

**"TURGENEV GIRLS" IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF RUSSIAN LITERATURE
(ON THE EXAMPLE OF THE ANALYSIS OF THE NOVEL BY I.S. TURGENEV
"THE NOBLE NEST")**

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Abstract: The article is devoted to the images of "Turgenev girls" in the development of Russian literature. I.S. Turgenev was able to notice and respond to all the acute phenomena of modernity, to put in his works those questions of Russian life that worried public thought.

Keywords: Turgenev girl, "Noble nest", folk morality, social problems, spirituality, self-sacrifice.

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"Systematic organization of work to increase the spirituality of youth, wide promotion of reading books" is one of the tasks in working with young people put forward by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan as five Priorities.

Russian Russian writer Ivan Sergeyeovich Turgenev's creative work played a huge role in the spiritual development of Russian society, in the history of Russian literature, and enriched world culture.

A lot of studies have been devoted to the study of I.S.Turgenev's creativity in modern literary science (Ostrovsky L., Pospelova G., Pixanova N.K., Rozanova I. N., Sokolova Y. M. etc.). At the same time, many of them note that one of the important issues that I.S.Turgenev raised in his works was the question of the family, family values and the role of women in the formation of moral values. It was with this that the problem of "Turgenev girls" was connected in a number of the writer's works.

I.S. Turgenev's reflections on the fate of the best people among the Russian nobility are the basis of the novel "The Noble Nest" (1858). After reading this novel, we can say that in it the noble environment is represented in almost all its states - from a provincial small-scale estate to the ruling elite. Turgenev condemns

everything in noble morality at its very core. How amicably in the house of Maria Dmitrievna Kalitina and in the whole "society" they condemn Varvara Pavlovna Lavretskaya for her foreign adventures, how they pity Lavretsky and, it seems, are ready to help him. But as soon as Varvara Pavlovna appeared and used the charms of her stereotypically flirtatious charm, everyone - both Maria Dmitrievna and the entire provincial beau monde - were delighted with her. This depraved creature, pernicious and distorted by the same noble morality, is quite to the taste of the highest noble environment.

Panshin, embodying the "exemplary" noble morality, is presented by the author without sarcastic pressure. One can understand Lisa, who for a long time could not properly define her attitude to Panshin and did not really resist Marya Dmitrievna's intention to marry her

to Panshin. He is courteous, tactful, moderately educated, knows how to keep up a conversation, he is even interested in art: he is engaged in painting - but he always writes the same landscape, composes music and poetry. "True, his giftedness is superficial: strong and deep experiences are simply not available to him. The real artist Lemm saw it, and Lisa, perhaps, only vaguely guessed about it. And who knows how Lisa's fate would have turned out if it hadn't been for the dispute. Ideological disputes always play a huge role in the composition of Turgenev's novels. Usually, in a dispute, either the beginning of a novel is formed, or the struggle of the parties reaches a culminating heat" [3, p. 29].

In the "Noble Nest", the dispute between Panshin and Lavretsky about the people is of great importance. Turgenev later remarked that it was a dispute between a Westerner and a Slavophile. This author's characteristic cannot be taken literally. The fact is that Panshin is a Westerner of a special, official kind, and Lavretsky is not a true Slavophile. In his attitude to the people Lavretsky is most similar to

Turgenev: he is not trying to give the character of the Russian people some simple, easily remembered definition. Like Turgenev, he believes that before inventing and imposing recipes for the organization of people's life, it is necessary to understand the character of the people, their morality, their true ideals. And at the moment when Lavretsky develops these thoughts, Lisa's love for Lavretsky.

Turgenev never tired of developing the idea that love, by its very deep nature, is a spontaneous feeling and any attempts to rationalize its interpretation are often simply tactless. But the love of most of his heroines - "Turgenev girls" - almost always merges with altruistic aspirations. They give their hearts to selfless, generous and kind people. Egoism for them, as well as for Turgenev, is the most unacceptable human quality.

"In the character of Lisa Kalitina, in her whole attitude, the beginning of folk morality is expressed even more clearly. With all her behavior, her calm grace, she

probably resembles Tatiana Larina more than all Turgenev's heroines" [4, p. 58].. But there is one property in her personality that is only outlined in Tatiana Pushkin, but which will become the main distinguishing feature of the type of Russian women that is commonly called "Turgenev". This property is dedication, readiness for self-sacrifice. Lisa's fate contains Turgenev's verdict on a society that kills everything pure that is born in it.

A favorite place of action in Turgenev's works is "noble nests" with the atmosphere of sublime experiences reigning in them. Their fate worries Turgenev. Therefore, the novel "Noble Nest" is imbued with a sense of anxiety for the fate of "noble nests".

We can say that this novel is imbued with the consciousness that "noble nests" are degenerating. Turgenev critically highlights the noble pedigrees of the Lavretskys and Kalitins, seeing in them a chronicle of serfdom, a bizarre mixture of "wild nobility" and aristocratic worship of Western Europe.

The collapse of the hero's illusions, the impossibility of personal happiness for him, are, as it were, a reflection of the social collapse that the nobility experienced during these years. "Turgenev girls" are ready to overcome any difficulties and adversities, for the sake of holy and pure love, for the sake of maintaining a relationship with a loved one.

"Nest" is a house, a symbol of the family, where the connection of generations is not interrupted. In the novel "The Noble Nest" this connection is broken, which symbolizes the destruction, the withering away of ancestral estates under the influence of serfdom. Turgenev hopes that all is not lost yet, and turns in the novel, saying goodbye to the past, to a new generation in which he sees the future of Russia. And he associates all the purest and most moral with the image of his "Turgenev girl".

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